

Forensic Genetic Genealogy in the Philippines: Are We Ready?

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Introduction

This paper seeks to evaluate whether Forensic Genetic Genealogy (FGG) is viable in the Philippines by looking into required infrastructure and science to come up with the conclusions this system offers and whether our current legal framework – jurisprudence, the Rules on DNA Evidence, and the Rules of Court

in general, could accommodate findings from FGG and be used, admitted, and appreciated as evidence in our jurisdiction.

Forensic Genetic Genealogy harbors three very familiar words, but as a whole, it might sound foreign even to those into Forensics. This is because this system – and we refer to it as a system more than as just a single test as will be shown later – though using well established methodologies, has only seen real world application in the recent decade. In fact, the United States Department of Justice had only issued and made effective its interim rules on Forensic Genetic Genealogy Searches and Analyses in November, 2019¹ which not only goes to show how new this system is in the field of forensics but also shows how this system as a field of forensics is growing.

The simplest way to describe this method is by taking one basic principle in DNA Science and that is that DNA Sources with common ancestors or familial ties would have several genetic loci similar and thus familial relations can be determined with a certain

¹ United States Department of Justice Interim policy ... (n.d.). Retrieved January 10, 2022, from <https://www.justice.gov/olp/page/file/1204386/download>

degree of specificity. This means that an unknown source of genetic material can be matched to his relatives who may be in a DNA database, so long as this database has enough data on persons of a specific area, or we can use DNA information of the willing relatives of a suspect who in themselves could not be tested for lack of sufficient cause to herald the person as a suspect.

The science of this system is more or less basic – this “includes the use of large genotype data sets, typically including hundreds of thousands of single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs), in combination with large public genealogy DNA databases in order to track biological relatives of an unknown donor by matching segments of shared DNA.”²

To best illustrate this method, we can look at one highly publicized success story, i.e. conviction of what was a cold case for decades, that was ultimately solved by way of FGG – the Golden State Killer.

² Tillmar A, Fagerholm SA, Staaf J, Sjölund P, Ansell R. Getting the conclusive lead with investigative genetic genealogy - A successful case study of a 16 year old double murder in Sweden. *Forensic Sci Int Genet.* 2021 Jul;53:102525. doi: 10.1016/j.fsigen.2021.102525. Epub 2021 May 8. PMID: 33991867.

The Golden State Killer

The story of the Golden State Killer is well described by several Youtube videos and articles. One particularly exhaustive article by ABCNEWS by Emily Shapiro and is heavily cited in this section of the paper is instructive.³

According Shapiro, all started sometime in the summer of 1976 in the eastern district of the Sacramento Country, California, USA where a string of sexual assaults against women and burglaries of jewelries and cash swept through this community.

However many contemporaneous pundits would describe this initial onslaught and the terrorizing effect it had as ephemeral not until the actual slew of killings took place sometime in February 1978 when this person, who was identified to be one person by way of his scope of activity and modus operandi in entry into these homes

³ Shapiro, E. (n.d.). The 'Golden State Killer': Inside the timeline of crimes. ABC News. Retrieved January 10, 2022, from <https://abcnews.go.com/US/inside-timeline-crimes-golden-state-killer/story?id=54744307>

shot and killed the couple Brian and Katie Maggiore, who according to several articles were merely walking their dog in the Sacramento area. After Brian Maggiore was shot, Katie Maggiore ran away and yelled for help, but DeAngelo caught up with her and shot her in the head, prosecutors said.

Shapiro continues to stay how “these burglaries continued in the East Bay area of Northern California, and then escalated into rapes and murders along the California coast, the FBI said. The "Golden State Killer" would often "attack couples, tie up both victims, rape the female, and then murder them," according to the FBI. On Dec. 30, 1979, Debra Manning and Robert Offerman were killed in Goleta, near Santa Barbara. Lyman and Charlene Smith were murdered in their Ventura home in March 1980. Charlene Smith was bound and raped, prosecutors said. The couple was later found dead by Lyman Smith's 12-year-old son, prosecutors said. On Feb. 5, 1981, 28-year-old Manuela Witthuhn was bound, raped and bludgeoned to death while home alone in Irvine in Southern California. Her body was found by her mother, prosecutors said. Sanchez was shot and then beaten to death, bludgeoned in the head two dozen times, prosecutors said. DeAngelo then bound

Domingo, raped her and beat her in the head more than 10 times, prosecutors said.

No crimes were attributed to the "Golden State Killer" from July 1981 until May 1986, when 18-year-old Janelle Cruz was killed. Cruz was bound, raped and bludgeoned in the face and head at her home, prosecutors said. That was his last known crime."⁴

Guerrini et al (2018) states that "For decades, California police tracked the Golden State Killer using traditional detective work, but all leads came to dead ends. Six years ago, however, investigators tried a different tactic. Instead of trying to identify the killer—a needle in an enormous haystack—they sought first to reduce the size of the haystack by identifying the killer's family. Investigators did so by uploading a genetic profile generated from DNA that had been collected from one of the crime scenes to genealogy websites that match users to their genetic relatives.

⁴ See Note 3

After years of searching and at least one failed attempt, investigators finally identified the extended family of the Golden State Killer using the website GEDmatch. GEDmatch, which is operated by a handful of genealogy hobbyists, compares users' genetic data (originally obtained from direct-to-consumer [DTC] genetic testing services like 23andMe and AncestryDNA) to identify genetic matches among them. The website's algorithm generated a partial match between the killer's DNA, which investigators submitted under a fake name, and the DNA of at least one distant relative.

Having substantially reduced the haystack, investigators were able to identify the needle by constructing family trees and scouring them for potential suspects. Investigators eventually zeroed in on DeAngelo and matched his genetic data, which was collected from an object that he discarded while under surveillance, to crime scene DNA.”⁵

⁵ Guerrini CJ, Robinson JO, Petersen D, McGuire AL (2018) Should police have access to genetic genealogy databases? Capturing the Golden State Killer and other criminals using a controversial new forensic technique. PLoS Biol 16(10): e2006906. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.2006906>

Requirements for FGG; DNA Technology and System Used

If we do take the Golden State Killer Investigation as our model in applying FGG for Criminal Investigation we can summarily come up with the requirement of the confluence of two main methodologies: DNA Analyses and a DNA Database.

In particular, the type of DNA Analyses we need is one that can determine familial relations – that is – a test or tests that can determine extent of relations between DNA samples. If this cannot be achieved, then the whole logical framework of Forensic Genetic Genealogy would not be realized.

The Supreme Court in the DNA Staple Case of PP v. Yatar⁶ stated: DNA is a molecule that encodes the genetic information in all living organisms. A person's DNA is the same in each cell and it does not change throughout a person's lifetime; the DNA in a person's blood is the same as the DNA found in his saliva, sweat, bone, the root

⁶ PP. v. Yatar. G.R. No. 150224. (May 19, 2004)

and shaft of hair, earwax, mucus, urine, skin tissue, and vaginal and rectal cells. Most importantly, because of polymorphisms in human genetic structure, no two individuals have the same DNA, with the notable exception of identical twins.

DNA Databases

FGG requires the use of a large genotype data sets, typically including hundreds of thousands of single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs), which should be fielded against a standard public genealogy DNA databases in order to track biological relatives of an unknown donor by matching those same segments of shared DNA. These loci matching and the extent of matching would be able to determine familial relations.

Therefore, there has to be that DNA Database that is of a public nature in order to arrive at relations as conclusions to aid investigations.

In the Philippines however, we do not have such a public/government sponsored database.⁷

PNP DNA Database

As early as 2015, the Philippine National Police Directorate for Investigation and Directive Management (DIDM) had releases a Directive with no. 2015-05⁸ for the “Collection of DNA Samples from Arrested Person and Persons under Custody and Registration of thei DNA Profiles into the PNP DNA Database.

The Rationale as follows, of the directive is of important note:

“DNA technology has proven to be an invaluable tool in the identification of al person. Law enforcement capabilities have been greatly improved with the use of DNA in tracing individuals who have commilled crimes. In cases where a suspect is identified

⁷ De Ungria, M., & Jose, J. (2010). Forensic DNA profiling and databasing: The Philippine experience. In R. Hindmarsh & B. Prainsack (Eds.), *Genetic Suspects: Global Governance of Forensic DNA Profiling and Databasing* (pp. 309-330). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. doi:10.1017/CBO9780511778193.016

⁸ PNP DIDM Directive No. 2015-05 (November 16, 2015)

suspect's DNA can be compared to the DNA evidence collected from the crime scene. The result of comparison will help establish whether or not the suspect is the perpetrator. In line with the recent events, it is through DNA that the identities of international terrorists Zulkifli bin Abdul Hir @ Marwan and Abdul Bast man were confirmed.

The collective effort of government security forces against terrorism and criminality in recent years had been significant. High profile SPSG, CNN, and CC personalities, most of whom were previously indicted for multiple non-bailable offenses had been taken into custody. As part of the booking procedure their biometrics such as fingerprints and photographs were obtained and subsequently recorded in existing database systems like the CLS Automated Fingerprint Identification System (AFIS) and the CIDG's Criminal Biometric Identification System (CBIS). However, it is remarkable to note that minimal attention was given in the collection and processing on the DNA specimens of these detainees. Case in point is the 61 high profile detainees arrested and currently detained at the Custodial Center of the HSS. None of them was swabbed for DNA specimen, nor so, tested.

Recidivism is one of the most fundamental concepts in criminal justice. Often persons who received sanctions for previous crimes relapse into criminal behavior. Registering the DNA profiles of individuals who are implicated in the commission of a crime including but not limited to arrested persons and persons under custody will provide expeditious and highly accurate mode of identification of wanted criminals

The PNP, in its mandate to serve and protect, is currently populating its DNA database With the acquisition of the Combined DNA Index System (CODIS) 2013. Crime Laboratory was able to build a DNA profile database currently used for routine casework analysis. At present, 5,694 DNA profiles from forensic stains victims, suspects and unidentified human remains are registered into the PNP DNA database Increasing the database content will maximize its potential in providing. accurate mode of identification of wanted criminals through the use DNA technology thus help achieve higher crime solution efficiency

In order to increase its database power and maximize its utilization, a policy on the collection and subsequent registration of DNA samples from arrested persons and persons under custody shall form part of the standard booking procedures.”⁹

There is a clear recognition and mandate to create the very same DNA Database that would make FGG possible even though we see that this Database, being that of persons deprived of liberty (PDL) would be most effective against recidivist activities since these are the persons who already have that DNA record. However, logically, this database, if FGG is employed could help in investigations if it so happens that the perpetrator of the crime being investigated is related to any of the tested and sampled PDLs.

This is a great step forward. But unfortunately, after 7 years from this directive, the PNP still does not have that database even though they reportedly already have existing equipment for that very purpose. House Bill No. 7215, or An Act Providing for the Establishment of the Philippine DNA Database System, was filed

⁹ See Note8

by Surigao del Norte Representative Robert Ace Barbers in 2018 but has not yet been passed into law.¹⁰

History of the Philippine Genome Center

This is taken from the About Page of the Philippine Genome Center's website: "In 2008, the Philippines hosted the Human Genome Organization Conference in the Asia Pacific. After this conference, University of the Philippines (UP) President Emerlinda R. Roman, created a committee to study the feasibility of setting up a Genome Center in the University. The committee consisted of then UP Vice President for Academic Affairs Amelia Guevara (Chair), Dr. Gisela Concepcion of the Marine Science Institute, UP Diliman; Dr. Carmencita Padilla of the UP College of Medicine, UP Manila; and Dr. Cynthia Saloma of the National Institute of Molecular Biology and Biotechnology, UP Diliman. The committee visited several genome centers in the region (Hong Kong, Taiwan, Singapore) and the United States to obtain insights towards the development of a Philippine Genome Center (PGC).

¹⁰ PNP Seeks DNA Database. (June 4, 2019)

<https://tribune.net.ph/index.php/2019/06/04/pnp-seeks-dna-database-system/>

During the development phase of the PGC, several major events led to its establishment – the Dengue outbreak that reached alarming rates, the SARS outbreak in Hong Kong and the H1N1 outbreak in Mexico, reinforcing the importance of genomics in providing new solutions.

An audience with President Gloria Macapagal-Arroyo in July 2009 paved for the first two grant awards of PGC – Dengue diagnostic test and H1N1 surveillance network through the Department of Science and Technology.

At the 1246th Board of Regents Meeting on July 31, 2009, the proposal for the establishment of the Philippine Genome Center was approved. It was established as a multidisciplinary institution that will combine basic and applied research for the development of health diagnostics, therapeutics, DNA forensics and preventive products, and improved crop varieties in the country.

PGC was formally launched on November 28, 2011 at the Shangri-la Hotel in Makati City. In his keynote address DOST Secretary

Mario G. Montejo shared that genomics can be a “game changing tool that can offer enormous rewards to the Filipinos” hence DOST will focus on genomics program on health, agriculture, livestock, fisheries and biodiversity. Two years after, PGC’s DNA Sequencing Core Facility was launched on September 24, 2013. Then was followed by the official launch of the Core Facility for Bioinformatics on April 14, 2014.”¹¹

Private DNA Databases

Much like in the case of the Golden State Killer, the Philippines could still employ FGG by posting the DNA samples in crimes against privately owned and regulated DNA Databases.

In the Golden State Killer case, they used GEDmatch which, as discussed in the previous sections, is privately managed by genetics enthusiasts and is, by its nature merely a public repository of DNA data acquire from private DNA processing companies such as 23andme and Ancestry.com.

¹¹ History of the Philippine Genome Center. .Philippine Genome Center.
<https://pgc.up.edu.ph/about/history/>

23andme and Ancestry.com are especially relevant to this study because these two companies come up with the exact kind of DNA data used in FGG – ancestry.

Companies such as 23andMe, Ancestry.com and National Geographic market these at-home DNA testing kits, offering to unlock your genetic secrets for the price of a group dinner at a nice restaurant and about half a teaspoon of spit.¹²

These, being private in nature, have strict privacy restrictions – on top of the fact that the companies are based in the US, and thus, seemingly beyond our court's jurisdiction.

However, 23andme has stated that about 80% of their clients are have opted to participate in genetic researches by releasing their genetic data to researchers.

¹² Letzter, Rafi. How Do DNA Ancestry Tests Really Work? (June 04, 2018)
<https://www.livescience.com/62690-how-dna-ancestry-23andme-tests-work.html>

There is also an option that the client can pull-out his or her data and deposit it in repositories like GEDMatch and make it wholly available to the public.

Infrastructure for FGG

If we look at the current state of Philippine infrastructure it would seem that FBB is viable to a certain degree.

In terms of DNA testing for genealogical purposes, the various medical, government and even university-based laboratories can so easily analyze the sample for that purpose.

There is no difference in the standard assays done on DNA for paternity, or identification which nonetheless looks at the sixteen loci in order to make matches.

The greater problem is the standard database against which we match the DNA sampled from crime scenes. It is just not enough. Unlike in the west, 2017-2018 saw a rise of interest in genealogical

testing.¹³ In the Philippines, we've only had the same service from minor companies, which had not penetrated popular culture.

Public consciousness of Genealogical Testing in the Philippines can be improved, perhaps after the pandemic. But before that happens, we would have to rely on datasets from a willing public or community which in itself poses problems, but this time, as to the Legal Framework of the Philippines.

Challenges akin to Philippine Legal Framework

Data Privacy and Search Warrants

One important issue that is met by many jurisdictions that employ FGG is the stumbling block as to privacy.

We look at the Data Privacy Law as follows:

¹³ <https://www.vox.com/recode/2020/2/13/21129177/consumer-dna-tests-23andme-ancestry-sales-decline>

Section 1. Short Title. – This Act shall be known as the "Data Privacy Act of 2012".

Section 2. Declaration of Policy. – It is the policy of the State to protect the fundamental human right of privacy, of communication while ensuring free flow of information to promote innovation and growth. The State recognizes the vital role of information and communications technology in nation-building and its inherent obligation to ensure that personal information in information and communications systems in the government and in the private sector are secured and protected.

Section 3. Definition of Terms. – Whenever used in this Act, the following terms shall have the respective meanings hereafter set forth:

xxx

(c) Data subject refers to an individual whose personal information is processed.

xxx

(g) Personal information refers to any information whether recorded in a material form or not, from which the identity of an individual is apparent or can be reasonably and directly ascertained by the entity holding the information, or when put together with other information would directly and certainly identify an individual.

(h) Personal information controller refers to a person or organization who controls the collection, holding, processing or use of personal information, including a person or organization who instructs another person or organization to collect, hold, process, use, transfer or disclose personal information on his or her behalf.

The term excludes:

(1) A person or organization who performs such functions as instructed by another person or organization; and

(2) An individual who collects, holds, processes or uses personal information in connection with the individual's personal, family or household affairs.

(i) Personal information processor refers to any natural or juridical person qualified to act as such under this Act to whom a personal information controller may outsource the processing of personal data pertaining to a data subject.

Xxx

(l) Sensitive personal information refers to personal information:

(1) About an individual's race, ethnic origin, marital status, age, color, and religious, philosophical or political affiliations;

(2) About an individual's health, education, genetic or sexual life of a person, or to any proceeding for any offense committed or alleged to have been committed by such person, the disposal of such proceedings, or the sentence of any court in such proceedings;

Xxx”

As can be surmised from the above sections of the Data Privacy Act, it is quite clear that DNA Genealogic data falls squarely within the ambit and coverage of this Act and thus, cannot be wantonly demanded even for legitimate purposes sans a court order determining the necessity of such information – by way of a search warrant.

Basic is the legal requirement of a finding of probable cause in order for a search warrant to be issued, determined by the court – hence, in order for there to be access of these databases holding the information we need to establish the conclusions of FGG. In this paradigm, we would need to establish that the database holder (private), does contain the necessary information we are looking for – there is a need of specificity which is antithetical to the point of FGG where we are necessary casting a wide net, and hope that we catch something. It is precisely why we resort to FGG because we have no way of establishing even a prima facie case against an individual.

Applying the Rules of DNA Evidence

One important legal question that's need resolution is whether or not the evidence brought about by FGG is DNA evidence by definition of the Rules.

You see, if you analyze it really carefully, FGG, at best, would tell us from a set of DNA data if the sample we collected is related to this DNA dataset from the databases.

At best, therefore, our conclusions would be the identification of the relatives of the sample source. In the same way that they identified the Golden State Killer by identifying only his 1st cousin in the database, and then made differentials as to all the possible persons in within that degree of relations with the person they matched and finally ending up with a short list. What happened was a DIRECT COMPARISON of a sample of one person who was a 1st cousin of the match they had in the DNA database which yielded then DNA evidence that identified the Killer himself.

What this means is that the DNA evidence in the FGG is not actually the evidence used to implicate the suspect – but was used to NARROW DOWN the search to a group of persons.

Is this admissible in evidence – yes because admissibility of DNA evidence has already been ruled so. However, is it sufficient in itself to make a conviction? No.

Even Direct DNA evidence, according to the rules is not sufficient in itself.

“Sec. 7. Assessment of probative value of DNA evidence. – In assessing the probative value of the DNA evidence presented, the court shall consider the following:

The chain of custody, including how the biological samples were collected, how they were handled, and the possibility of contamination of the samples;

The DNA testing methodology, including the procedure followed in analyzing the samples, the advantages and disadvantages of the procedure, and compliance with the scientifically valid standards in conducting the tests;

The forensic DNA laboratory, including accreditation by any reputable standards-setting institution and the qualification of the analyst who conducted the tests. If the laboratory is not accredited, the relevant experience of the laboratory in forensic casework and credibility shall be properly established; and

The reliability of the testing result, as hereinafter provided.

The provisions of the Rules of Court concerning the appreciation of evidence shall apply suppletorily.”¹⁴

The Supreme Court has recognized the following key US principles:

“If scientific, technical, or other specialized knowledge will assist the trier of fact to understand the evidence or to determine a fact in issue, a witness qualified as an expert by knowledge, skill, experience, training, or education, may testify thereto in the form of an opinion or otherwise.

¹⁴ Rules on DNA Evidence, Philippines. A.M. No. 06-11-5-SC. (2 October 2007)

Daubert cautions that departure from the Frye standard of general acceptance does not mean that the Federal Rules do not place limits on the admissibility of scientific evidence. Rather, the judge must ensure that the testimony's reasoning or method is scientifically valid and is relevant to the issue. Admissibility would depend on factors such as (1) whether the theory or technique can be or has been tested; (2) whether the theory or technique has been subjected to peer review and publication; (3) the known or potential rate of error; (4) the existence and maintenance of standards controlling the technique's operation; and (5) whether the theory or technique is generally accepted in the scientific community."¹⁵

What needs to be done

There is a need to establish a DNA Database that is available for private persons who wish to volunteer their own personal DNA data which shall be included in the matching process.

¹⁵Herrera v. Herrera. G.R. No. 148220 (June 15, 2005)

Incentive programs that support the expansion of the said database to the general public should also be instituted in order to widen the scope of the database and thus the matching process.

Lastly, as to the DNA Database, government employees should be made to submit themselves to DNA profiling to aid the database. At the end of the day, the Supreme Court has been clear that this act does not necessarily go against one's right against self incrimination, and therefore, should not be a problem at all. Anyway, personal data of government employees are sequestered through forms and submissions like the Civil Service Personal Data Sheet and the Statement of Assets, Liabilities and Net Worth.

As to DNA testing itself, for private persons, the issue is as to cost, more than anything else. If we want a large database of DNA information to use for FGG, we need to make DNA profiling more accessible even to those who would have it done freely and willingly -n private persons.

23andme and Ancestry cost at most \$79 as of this writing, while a paternity test in the Philippines would set a person back about \$400

dollars. This staggering difference is a deterrent for testing and should be looked into unless government facilities would offer the same services themselves, at expectedly lower prices.

The goal here, to make FGG viable as an option in investigations, when there is no suspect in mind in criminal cases, is really to expand that DNA Database more than anything else and if we can do that, and if we do that legally, then cold cases might just be reopened and we might see convictions of the actual perpetrators of crimes.

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